

SCIENTIFIC GRAMMAR BASED ON THE INTEGRATION OF ENGLISH AND RESEARCH

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Abstract. This article discusses how to teach a number of basic grammatical issues, including nouns and their usage, that arise in the process of writing scientific articles for researchers working in science. This paper covers only the problems found in research paper, which is why, the use of nouns is analyzed in terms of how they are used in scientific texts rather than how they are used in general spoken language.

Keywords: English, research, scientific English, noun, integration.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the scientific method is to clearly describe complex ideas. [1] Complex thought requires complex language. It is known that nouns clearly express thoughts and create a more meaningful context. As the academic levels increase, so does the complexity of the nouns and the word combinations they participate in to express complex and difficult concepts. Therefore, complex noun phrases are a crucial academic language feature that learners need to understand, and it is important to know how words are put together to create meaning. [2]

METHODOLOGY

While conducting research for this article, we reviewed articles written in a variety of disciplines. As a result, we found that each author uses very unique methods in the field of study, which are not similar to other fields of science and do not conform to common standards. A clear example of this is the use of *we*. In some subjects, the pronouns *we* (and even *I*) are freely used; their use in other subjects is strictly limited. In addition, another issue is related to the use of the article phrase - where in one subject *the* and *a/an* are mandatory in certain cases, but in others it is not necessary. Another example: punctuation rules, particularly regarding abbreviations and measurements, vary considerably from author to author and journal to journal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Now, we shall look at the specific cases related to nouns, their usage and style in research papers. The blue color indicates an applicable or preferred way, while the red one refers to non-applicable cases.

If the two nouns indicate a single entity in a *noun+of+noun* construction, the first noun is made plural.

Several points of view have been put forward in the literature.	Several point of views have been put forward in the literature.
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Nouns that act as adjectives are not made plural.

Car production is rising, but car sales are falling. = The production of cars is rising but the sales of cars are falling.	Cars production is rising, but cars sales are falling.
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A noun which follows a number (or an implied number) is used in the singular form when acting as an adjective.

This work is part of a three- phase study into psychotic behavior amongst TEFL teachers.	This work is part of a three- phases study into psychotic behavior amongst TEFL teachers.
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-fold, which is a suffix to indicate a specified number of parts or times, does not have a plural -s.

The increase was 3-fold .	The increase was 3 folds .
= There was a 3-fold increase.	There was a 3 folds increase.

People requires a plural verb. *persons* is often used as a more formal version of *people*. *persons* is frequently found in medical and psychology research papers, or when talking about the capacity of a machine to hold a certain number of persons. In other cases, *people* is often more appropriate particularly when it refers to people in general, rather than a subset.

Title: Prevention of heart disease in older persons	
Title: A hypnotherapy treatment for persons prone to criminal activities	
Title: Job satisfaction – How do people feel about their jobs?	Title: Job satisfaction – How do persons feel about their jobs?
The police are often perceived as being racist.	The police is often perceived as being racist.

Scientific / technical acronyms whose last letter stands for a countable noun behave like other countable nouns. They thus require an article when used in the singular, and an -s when used in the plural.

Access requires a PIN (personal identification number).	Access requires PIN (personal identification number).
The number of purchases of CDs is only 1% of what is was 25 years ago.	The number of purchases of CD is only 1% of what is was 25 years ago.

If the noun is followed by *of* (i.e. to add further details), then this noun is preceded by *a / an*.

An analysis of the data showed that ...	Analysis of the data showed that ...
... with a probability of 0.25	... with probability 0.25.

To express the plural of certain uncountable words, sometimes you need to choose another word.

We need a program / an app .	We need a software .
We need a software application .	
We have a training course tomorrow.	We have a training tomorrow.

Some uncountable nouns can be used in a countable way when preceded by an adjective.

This does not imply prior	She has a good knowledge of
knowledge of ...	English.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is particularly important for reviewers and editors to be aware of the general lack of consistency in the use of English in academic texts. They may find examples of constructions and word usage in the paper they are revising that defy the normal rules of English, but what would be considered incorrect in a particular situation in another discipline. Therefore, we prefer to consider the grammatical cases that we consider and recommend in this article as "guidelines" rather than "rules". These recommendations are based on experience [3] gained from reading thousands of manuscripts, rather than any specific rules that can be found in other grammar books or on the Internet.

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